

Systems and Software Safety and Security

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Abstract—Security issue and the importance of the function of police to provide practical and psychological contexts in the community has been the main topics among researchers, police and security circles and this subject require to review and analysis mechanisms within the police and its interaction with other parts of the system for providing community safety. This paper examine national and social security in the Internet.

Keywords—Internet National security Social security

I. Introduction

TODAY, Internet expansion created a field that a wide range of information without any geographical limits and beyond will be released around the world and dramatically to become a medium of communication and information. While the audience and Internet users steady increase an equally. Characteristic and features of Internet and publishing easily and access on various information on the web including text, sound and image and graphic data intensified that in some cases information contain malicious and harmful contents is published on the web that in the field of child abuse, promoting violence and corruption, drug dealing, and detrimental, promoting private information of individuals and organizations, use the web information in order to terrorist purposes need to control web content. But this monitor on publish information in different communities based on cultural and political policies of each society has different aspects. In some western societies are a greater emphasis on no abuse of personal information of individuals and prevent to publish the sexual images of children and preventing terrorist access to specific information, but Internet content control in eastern and religious communities is above and beyond and also include intense monitoring on distribution of political ideas in the global network. What makes the basis difference on filtering for each country, the fundamental and interest values in each category in that country. Overall, we can say that the number of countries in the region and the world face somehow the issue of Internet filtering and censorship is relatively significant.

A. National Security

When national security is that threats from outside are threatened values and vital interests in the country. In this conditions, individuals have a major role in national security. In general, security define to feel the anxiety relief, anxiety, fear or feel relaxed and assured [1]. Phenomena that may cause fear and disrupt people calm, are complex and numerous. With time and changes in human needs, new variables appearing e into the security arena. If during the cold

war, the field of security were theorize in the military dimension and only among the two superpowers. Today the field of security theorize between all governments and international actors, including new media, transnational organizations, criminal organizations, nongovernmental groups, multinational corporations in various fields of economic, military, cultural, environmental, social, etc. Today the government has superior power and to impose security and rule, creates tools and organizations that military and police forces, one of their most prominent. Police and security forces in different societies according to cultural conditions, social, political, economic and population are facing with challenging and diverse crimes such as theft, smuggling, murder, fraud and etc and dealing with these abnormalities requires a force that many countries have placed upon it the name of the police. People are very sensitive and accurate than type and amount of police action in dealing with the actions disrupt security, dignity and integrity of their lives and rate of their confidence in the police role is important in their satisfaction[2]. Police to provide security and peace in society, created an organization based on its withdrawal from the threatening environment, tools and methods of threat, strategies and tactics to provide objective is ahead. However, police is constant, but security environment, tools and methods of threat and security are changing.

B. Social Security

Today, the necessity and importance of social security in different areas who are not covered, because of all of the life facilities can overshadowed if safety is not be. This subject is considered that no human is able to provide complete security, thus he lives in society that can cooperate with others for social security. Social sphere is related to personal privacy that person in connection with other people in society and In this areas is maintaining person security or threatened. Urban unrest, criminal offense and honor and dignity of individuals, social areas are that affect on individuals security[3]. Waves defines social security: "the ability of society to protect its fundamental characteristics under changing conditions and real threats". He emphasize on relationship between identity and community [4]. In the community, people know your salary that is part of social security and can be guaranteed social security. In this regard, citizens are required to preserve their rights, and law enforcement in accordance with community norms and values. Plans in the form of social security is executed, indicate that some values violated the law try to deal with this number, because, ignoring these norms in fact is insult to the values of society. In the past, social security with the ability to maintain traditional patterns of language, culture, religion, values, new and diverse social order could be provided for people. Family, religion, traditional customs and beliefs were caused social and psychological security for individuals,

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means a family support social and psychological security of persons, but the wide variation in the family and other institutions ,traditional social security reviewing and put people at risk of norms, values and new identities. Today, sociologists emphasis on the concept of social order, and believe that with the social order of individuals and society components, functions can be performed easily and instability in social order cause to disrupt functional role of individuals in society , in fact one of the conditions of social security is social order that if there is security order, social security can be imagined.

In general. concept of security in software approaches, including values security and social identities that because non-objective nature, is no reaction ,while this sense means in the hardware approach was not considered external threat. Hard threats are tangible and along with reaction and is motivating. Security Reference in hard threats areas, are governments, while the security reference in software threats is transnational environment and global identity .

II. COMPUTER CRIMES AND ITS HISTORY

Internet, world wide web is that the various computer networks to connect to each other with using different hardware and software and with connections contracts and email addresses assign each of them provide to fast and extensive communication between people who are connected to the network and data exchange between them as text, sound, image and video allows[5]. Recently a new term called computer crime has been argued that imply the use of computer technology to commit crimes or acts is illegal. In other words, Internet crime refers to the activities in which computers, telephones and other technological elements are employed for the unauthorized entry on computer data and distribution of viruses, fraud and sexual abuse of children and women. In other words, cyber crimes, which are a type of internet crime, including crimes that occur in cyber space. Internet crime experts , such crimes have been identified in three categories :The first floor are crimes in which computers are located crime target, such as information steal that the one of the biggest concerns for many governments and companies. In here, the offender tries to unauthorized achieve computers and information systems of people or and misuse it Second floor are the crimes that criminals use computer as tools and Commit traditional crimes in which the reality happens, and third floor are crimes in which use of the computer is not important but makes it easy. For example, when the perpetrators use the computer to send letters, maps or send pornographic images to trap their victims, or drop them in crime scene [6].

In 1990, expanding of international broadcasters and satellite communications, third generation of computer crimes as internet crimes are in cyberspace. Users can access any electronic information service , regardless of the information and services which is located in point the world. Cyber environment provide important economic activity and necessary tool to perform all business transactions and internationally without human direct intervention. Within the boundaries of user activity was not limited on physics borders of home or even a work, country level and in a low-

cost, user can meet people to exchange information in the world , without know from place of person Insufficient security of technology with its virtual nature provided a good opportunity for evil individuals. The most worrying of aspect of cyberspace is distribute quick information, for example, in a short time, the part of information that can exploited is discovered [7].

A. Internet criminals

In many cyber crimes, the offender is a young person illegally enter the computer of individuals or companies for adventure, fun and entertainment and creating problems for people and the users networks. But sometimes adult offender who is looking for important information and stealing and selling them. In this case, the criminals mainly are people employed in companies and corporations have access to information, therefore they are attacked system from within. Because, internet criminals no physical presence at the crime, so arrest him is difficult. Even in most cases, the offender may be a point in the country and away from the act. Due to the nature of internet crime, in most cases, victims are different governments, agencies and companies that are looking for program and their special interests . This sometimes is caused slow process of legislation against cyber crime [6]. Generally, internet criminals can be classified into three groups:

1-Hacker: In 1970 decade, the term hacker was refers to a intelligent person is programming . Later, in 1980 decade, the term mean someone who was expertise influence on new systems influential . Today, objective is deter hackers, the media authorities such as government agencies and police force, the term means person committed a crime related to technology. It is true that curious hackers can be inadvertently caused considerable losses, but the search for finding information, not revenge or hurting others, a factor is that makes hackers follow entertainment ruthlessly .

2-Crackers: Crackers are sinister hackers. They penetrate up to sabotage the system, disturb computer viruses , they can delete or destruct files . Embezzlement, tricks and industrial espionage (theft a company's confidential information) only a small part is crackers.

3-Telephone Ferric : other forms of computer crimes are Telephone Ferric . Ferric rather than access to computer systems, through telephone lines beat in cyber patrol. Ferric through the first of hackers emerged in 1970. One of the events that appearing by the Ferric in 1977 related to police department in the New York city , Ferric penetrate the office phone system and had been changed carefully the content recorded who saying welcomed of callers, In New recordings content were told that police officers are eating bread and cookies and drinking coffee and not answering the phone, this message note on callers that call the 119 1 number in emergency [7 , 8]

4-Internet espionage: Internet espionage like a classical espionage observe business, commercial, economic, political, military secrets and disclosure , transfer and use them. the

person committed a crime with disclosure these secrets, makes military, financial, commercial Losses. This crime is faced national security with the risk.

5-Internetg sabotage: This crime is a lot like destroy crime , offender target is disrupting in the economic and political system in the country .In fact, modification, suppression, or unauthorized delete computer data or operations to disrupt the system operation

6-Computer fraud: Import, change, eliminate or suppression of computer data or programs can be done in order to political and economic goals can be done. computer fraud is data fraud .In the computer fraud, act committed affect data, except that data, the nature of the documents not normal.

III. CONCLUSION

Security is always the most important concern. Since the early humans, the security has been introduced as the most fundamental of life after food and water. Perhaps the caveman early human as first evolution of human on earth was on this basis base to create permanent for avoid the dangers of life. Alongside other innovations to improve the human condition, ways to establish security to promote and people looking to create solutions for increase their social life security . Concept of security is immunity from invasion and mandatory possession without consent. security for people means that people are not fear and afraid than their legitimate rights and freedoms and legitimate rights does not threaten . Police efforts to create social security in the Internet showed that there are missing rings that cause crime and corruption that police and security forces had discovered. Therefore, identification and uproot this roots will be beneficial for prevention of crime and social security

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